

A STUDY ON VIRRUDHA AHARA (INCOMPATIBLE DIET) AS NIDAN OF AAMVAT

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INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, aamvata is explained as a disease where vitiated vata and kapha dosha gets accumulated in the trika sandhi and causes pain and stiffness in the joints 1. Amongst the various nidan of amvata mentioned in Ayurveda classics, virrudha ahar is also mentioned as an important cause 2.

As per Charak Samhita, those food substances or medicines which increase dosha's in their own sthana but does not expel the dosa from the body are called viruddha ahar 3. In other words those food substances and combinations which induce deteriorating action on the body tissues i.e dhatu can be called virrudha ahar.

18 types of viruddh ahar are mentioned in the classical text they are desha virrudha, kala virrudha, agni virrudha, matra

virrudha, satmaya viruddh, anila viruddh, sanskar virrudha, virya virrudha, koshta virrudha, avastha virrudha, kram virrudha, Parihara virrudha, upchara virrudha, paka virrudha, samyoga virrudha, hriday virrudha, sampad virrudha, vidhi virrudha. 4 The aim of the study is to find the possibility of relationship of virrudha ahar as nidan of aamvata and to know the specific virrudha ahar which have adverse effect for people suffering from aamvata.

METHODOLOGY

An analytical study was done on 10 patients of Rheumatoid arthritis in G.A.C.H guwahati, Assam. Patients were adults between age 18 to 60 years, who were diagnosed patients of Rheumatoid arthritis as per ACR/EULAR criteria for Rheumatoid arthritis and these patients

had symptoms similar to *aamvata*. The patients were selected as per necessary formalities under strict protocol to prevent bias and reduce the error in the study. Detailed history regarding the diet (*ahar*) were taken into consideration in a specially designed proforma.

Inclusion criteria

1. Age- 18 to 60 years
2. Gender- both gender
3. Willing to participate in the study

Exclusion criteria

1. Not willing to participate in the study.
2. Pregnant and lactating women
3. Subjects with immunocompromised states like HIV, tuberculosis, hepatitis B and C etc
4. Subjects with malignancy

Evaluation measures

2010 ACR/ EULAR classification criteria for Rheumatoid arthritis-

A. Joint involvement

1 large joints	0
2-3 large joints	1
1-3 small joints	2
4-10 small joints	3
>10 joints	5

B. Serology

Negative RF and negative ACPA	0
Low positive RF or low positive ACPA	2
High positive RF or high positive ACPA	3

C. Acute phase reactants

Normal CRP and normal ESR	0
Abnormal CRP or abnormal ESR	1

D. Duration of symptoms

<6 weeks	0
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>or= 6 weeks

1

The criteria are meant to be applied in patients with atleast one swollen joint, after the exclusion of other causes of synovitis. Patients with a score > or = 6 are classified as Rheumatoid arthritis. Also subjects with typical bone erosion can be classified as Rheumatoid arthritis regardless of score.

R F- rheumatoid factor

ACPA- anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies

Assessment criteria

1. All the specific Virrudha aharaja hetu as mentioned in Charak samhita were taken under consideration.
2. For assessment of intake, food frequency questionnaire for a period of 7 days have been employed as follows-
 - a. Frequency of intake once in a month = 0
 - b. Once in a week = 1
 - c. 2-3 times in a week = 2
 - d. 4 times in a week = 3
 - e. 5 times in a week = 4
 - f. Everyday intake = 5
3. For assessment, the virrudha aharaja nidans have been put in a specially designed proforma in terms of modern day foods.
4. Data above 50% of occurrence rate have been taken into consideration for the study.

RESULTS

Observation and statistical analysis.

Table 01: Prevalence of virrudha aharaja nidans in the study.

Sl no.	Virrudha ahar type	Modern day food, local names, activity	Number of observation	Percentage
1.	Desha virrudha (In anup desha)	Cold water	4	8
		Ice cream	3	6
		Cold drinks	4	8
		Fruit juice	5	10
		Cold custard	0	0
2.	Kala virrudha (in summer)	Green chillies	20	40
		Samosa	7	14
		Bhut jolokia	4	8

		Boiler chicken	15	30
3.	Agni virrudha	Spices Oily food	2 3	4 6
4.	Matra virrudha	Honey+ gur in equal quantity	0	0
5.	Satmaya virrudha	Taking food opposite to their taste	0	0
6.	Dosha virrudha	Taking food opposite to individual dosha	1	2
7.	Sanskar virrudha	Pressure cooker cooked food	26	52
8.	Virya virrudha	Fish mixed with milk	0	0
9.	Kostha virrudha For krura kostha For mridu kostha	Small quantity of food, manda guna Large quantity of food, guru guna	2 3	4 6
10.	Avastha virrudha For active person For lazy person	Dry fruits Ghee	1 4	2 8
11.	Kram virrudha	Water intake before a meal	5	10
12.	Parihar virrudha	Having contraindicated food	5	10
13.	Upachar virrudha	Taking cold water with ghee	4	8
14.	Paka virrudha	Half cooked rice Uncooked rice Overcooked rice Burnt rice	0 0 1 2	0 0 2 4
15.	Samyoga virrudha	Amla rasa+ milk	0	0
16.	Hriday virrudha	Undesireable food	2	4
17.	Sampad virrudha	Overripe fruit Juice of unripe fruit	4 1	8 2
18.	Vidhi virrudha	Milk+ banana Excess sugar Curd in evening	3 5 3	6 10 6

CONCLUSION

The study shows consumption of pressure cooker cooked food(52%) has the highest incidence rates. This virrudha ahara ja hetu seem to be common in modern days. Most people consume this virrudha ahar in daily diet but the symptoms of aamvata may not appear immediately but can appear in the long term consumption. Pressure cooker cooked food can lead to a significant loss of heat -sensitive nutrients like Vitamin C and folate, along with water soluble vitamins leaching into cooking liquid. While it enhances digestibility for beans, it may overcook delicate vegetables, reducing their nutrient density and causing starch breakdown.

Rest of the items with an incidence rate below 50% are considered insignificant and hence not recorded as predominant in the study.

Hence this study indicates for prevention of amvata in a person one should avoid excessive intake in the above mentioned virrudha ahara nidan. Also for curative purpose the above mentioned etiological factor can be taken into consideration from an Ayurvedic perspective.

The study shows possibility of relationship of virrudha ahar as nidana of amvata.

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